

Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme - Andhra Pradesh: A Critical Review of Implementation in Guntur District

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Mahatma Gandhi's NREGA has had a significant impact on social protection, livelihood security, and democratic empowerment, making it a powerful weapon for inclusive growth in rural India. The Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA), which enfranchised workers and became a landmark in world history, provided the largest employment program in human history in the last 15 years. Crores of poor people have been waiting for a long time to benefit from the government's initiative. The success of MGNREGA will be assessed by taking into account the number of people employed and different types of people employed from 2006-07 to 2019-20. The present study examines two mandals (Veldurthi & Durgi mandals) of Guntur district. This study was done especially on those who got 100 days of work benefits. It was also examined to what extent the employment guarantee was implemented.

Keywords: MGNREGA, right to work, employment, implementation

While India's economy has grown significantly throughout the 1990s, the rural poor have continued to relocate or take on odd employment. 68% of India's poorest citizens—who make up two-thirds of the population—live in rural areas. Currently, roughly 29.5% of rural Indians are thought to be living in poverty (Rangarajan Committee, 2014). In India, caste, employment position, gender, and land ownership are all risk factors for rural poverty. The most difficult issue for planners and policymakers appears to be creating jobs, especially in rural areas. For some years now, the employment situation has gotten worse. By producing new job opportunities each year, one of the key goals of the Five-Year Plans is to end poverty in rural areas. Moreover, the number of jobless people in rural areas is rising, and people are still moving to the metropolis. Low wages and rising unemployment have a negative impact on the rural work force. Following independence, the government implemented specific initiatives to augment employment prospects and initiatives to boost labour use in agriculture in an effort to improve the situation of rural labourers. The policies that have been put in place thus far to boost the agriculture sector's capacity to absorb labour have not yet proven

to be effective. The National Sample Survey Organization estimates that 300 million Indians are living in abject poverty. The majority of them survive by exploiting the natural resource base and engaging in casual, unskilled labour. Due to their dependence, they are more susceptible to crises like disease, natural catastrophes, and climate change, all of which have a negative impact on their ability to find employment and escape the cycle of poverty. Programs for direct employment, self-employment, social security, housing, constructing rural infrastructure, and managing land resources for reducing poverty are given by the Ministry of Rural Development. Several programmatic interventions have been advocated since the First Five Year Plan. Certain groups of the rural population, particularly unskilled, casual, and manual workers, have not been significantly impacted by these measures despite advances in employment generation in rural areas over the years. This is primarily due to the fact that rather than producing useful assets, these development programmes typically just offer temporary employment opportunities. The government is forced to promise jobs for a year and minimum wages because there is no assurance of employment or payment of wages for long periods of time.

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With nearly 75 years of experience in other rural employment programmes conducted in the nation, National Rural Employment Guarantee Act is not India's first paid employment programme. Since the introduction of the first programme, the Rural Works Programme, in the 1960s, the Indian government has carried out a number of pay employment programmes. This scheme was followed by several others, including the National Food for Work Program (1977), the Crash Scheme for Rural Employment (1971), the Training of Rural Youth for Self-Employment (1979), the National Rural Employment Program (1980), and the Jawahar Rozgar Yojana (1989), (2004). In 2005, the National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (NREGA) was established because despite the implementation of such programmes, rural poverty did not decrease.

The source of all problems in society is poverty. A nation cannot prosper unless its citizens are freed from extreme hunger and

poverty. The only way to integrate the economically downtrodden sections of society into the fabric of the nation is through an inclusive approach. The government launched an innovative programme named MGNREGA in this regard to empower the nation's rural and poor citizens. MGNREGA is seen as a "Perfect Solution" for ending rural poverty and creating jobs by increasing demand for labourers in rural areas (Jena & Ghosh, 2014).

MGNREGA was launched in 2006 with the primary objective of poverty alleviation, providing work for 100 days a year to all rural households whose adults are willing to perform unskilled manual labor at minimum wages. Every year, on an average, 23.2 billion work days are generated, 5 crore rural families are guaranteed employment and 9 crore adults-half of whom are women and the other half belong to Scheduled Tribes-are also guaranteed employment. This represents a significant effort in social inclusion (Goyal, 2014).

In this study, we analyze the impact of NREGS in 6 villages selected from Durgi and Veldurthi mandals each with more than 100 working days from Gurazala, a potential (MGNREGS) revenue division in Guntur district. The present study discusses how the employment guarantee scheme is implemented.

A study was conducted on the effectiveness of the National Rural Employment Guarantee Scheme in Guntur district of Andhra Pradesh. Migration to other areas is also taking place for stable livelihood. 100 days of work for each family in a financial year, and full wages are earned for employed laborers who believe in this scheme. NREGS can address the problems of inter-state migration in Guntur district with a legal guarantee of at least 100 days of employment in a financial year when other employment opportunities are scarce.

Considering that the MGNREGA project affects a significant portion of the circle of people and beneficiaries in rural areas, it is considered important to examine whether those people are actually aware of the program or not. In this regard, a micro study was conducted in 6 village panchayats of Gurazala division of Guntur district to know the sentiments and awareness of the people regarding MGNREGA program.

Review of Literature

Verma et al. (2025) An Analysis of Socio-Economic Impact of the Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MNREGA) on Beneficiaries in the State of Haryana, the analysis indicates that the average annual household expenditure increased from ₹85,000 before MNREGA enrollment to ₹94,000 after its implementation, reflecting a positive shift in income levels. The rise in total household income can partly be attributed to the earnings from MNREGA, which contributed around 12% to the overall income.

This limited contribution is largely due to the fact that households, on average, worked only about 56 days under MNREGA-well below the stipulated 100 days. The primary reason is that MNREGA is not the first employment preference for rural households. Agriculture and other alternative occupations remain more attractive because they provide food security and offer comparatively higher wages than MNREGA.

Murugan and Anshida (2024) Impact of MGNREGA among the livelihoods of rural people the study clearly highlights that MGNREGA has played a vital role in enhancing the livelihoods of

rural households in the selected villages of Coimbatore district. By generating an average of 78.2 days of employment per household annually at a daily wage rate of ₹272, the scheme has effectively contributed to increasing household income and reducing economic vulnerability, especially during agricultural lean seasons.

The program has also strengthened rural resilience by improving access to essential services such as food, education, and healthcare. Statistical evidence indicates a significant rise in household income, reaffirming MGNREGA's role as an important social safety net for rural communities.

Furthermore, the scheme has had a notable impact on women's empowerment, promoting greater financial independence, active participation in household and community decision-making, and increased confidence in public and workspaces.

Sunitha et al. (2020) the Covid-19 epidemic is taken into account when this essay is prepared. How useful will MGNREGA be in the event of a pandemic? Many people without steady jobs returned to their villages as the virus spread owing to the national lockdown since they had no other means for support. Participation in MGNREGA programmes among returned migrants begins. This report's authors examine MGNREGA work distribution and demand patterns. The author also predicts three months' worth of trends. The information is gathered from secondary sources and taken into account for the entire nation. The demand for work in the period 2019-20 climbed by 59.32% in May, 63.16% in June, and 57.73% in July. especially starting in May 2020. As a result, the union budget included additional cash for rural developmental activities as it was impossible to employ more than twice as many people without effective funding distribution. The author concluded that MGNREGA could meet demand and that job needs will increase.

Objectives of the Study

The objective of the present paper is to make a comprehensive study of MGNREGA on employment generation in rural Guntur district. The paper highlighted how far MGNREGA has reached the wage earners to know things like how many working days each family can get.

- To know the Impact of MGNREGS.
- To know the wage rate and man-days getting of the Household
- To find out whether all job card holders are getting work

The present study conducted in Guntur district of Andhra Pradesh, examined the impact of the Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA) on the socio-economic status of participants from marginalized communities.

(Growth of total the employment generated by MGNREGS. 2) Growth in the share of women in MGNREGS. 3) Growth in the Share of SC/ST Households in MGNREGS).

Method

The study considers both primary and secondary sources of data. The researcher gathered information on individual asset development, community asset generation, and long-term sustainability by conducting interviews according to a predetermined schedule and doing focus group discussions. For this paper 220 wage seekers who have worked for at least 2 years and 100 days in the last four years from 2016-17 to 2019-20 have been selected. Wage seekers from 6gram panchayats in 2 mandals of Veldurthi and Durgi mandals of Gurazala Revenue Division were selected. The sample was selected using purposive multiple stratified random sampling method.

Primary Data

The study was based on primary data collected from 220 households in 6-gram panchayats of excellent performing mandals in the district. The primary data has been gathered through administering sample surveys with the help of structured intervention schedule to interview the respondents. Interview schedules were designed in order to collect data on respondent demographics such as age, education, caste, style of dwelling, type of family, size of family, size of land holding, occupation, and family income.

Secondary Data

The secondary data was collected from published and unpublished sources, including the official website of MGNREGA, Ministry of Rural Development, Government of India; books; referred journals; periodicals; publications; various monitoring and evaluation reports of the Ministry of Panchayat Raj and Rural Development (Govt. of India); Government of A.P Report; various operational guidelines and notifications of the Govt., research institution, i.e., NIRD, on the other hand.

Statistical Tools Adopted

In the current study, statistical tools such as percentage, mean, standard deviation (SD), were utilised for data analysis and interpretation. The SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) Package was used to process the research data and analyse the results.

Procedure

This study collected data from two mandals in Guntur district as part of a PhD thesis on the impact of MGNREGS on marginalized groups. The data was collected from households that completed 100 days of work over a four-year period, with a focus on those that completed at least two years of work. The analysis is based on this data and is presented in the following sections.

Results and Discussion

This study collected data from beneficiaries of the MGNREGS in Veldurthi and Duggirala mandals of Guntur district. The analysis focuses on the benefits of wage employment and other benefits under NREGS, such as vermicomposting, land development, and horticulture. The study also examines the impact of the scheme on migration, number of working days, and wages earned per year. Specifically, the analysis discusses:

- The number of working days and wages earned per year
- The number of households that completed 100 days of work per year
- The benefits availed by beneficiaries, including vermicomposting, land development, and horticulture
- The impact of the scheme on migration

The findings are presented in detail, providing insights into the effectiveness of the MGNREGS in improving the livelihoods of rural households in the study area.

Impact of MGNREGS on the Respondents

Table 1

Details of Benefits got from MGNREGS

Sr. No	Benefit	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Wage Employment	130	59.09

2	Vermicompost	18	8.18
3	IHHL	16	7.27
4	Land Development	43	19.54
5	Soak Pits	07	3.18
6	Form Pond	04	1.81
7	Horticulture	02	0.90
Total		220	100.00

Note. Source: Primary data

The distribution of households based on the benefits obtained from MGNREGS is presented in Table 1. Among the different benefits, 59 per cent of households benefitted from wage employment and about 19.5 per cent of households benefitted from land development. While 8 per cent of households benefitted from vermicompost, 7 per cent of households benefitted from IHHL, 3 per cent of households benefitted from soak pits, 2 per cent of households benefitted from form pond, and 0.90 per cent of households benefitted from horticulture.

Table 2

Distribution based on whether the Household Income Increased

Sr. No	Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	100 days wage employment secured	208	94.54
2	Self-Employment - Business established	12	5.45
Total		220	100.00

Note. Source: Primary data

In Table 2, responses based on ways through which household income increased have been presented. It is evident from the data that more than 95 per cent of households responded that their household income increased by way of 100 days of wage employment secured, whereas 5 per cent of households responded by stating that their household income increased by way of Self Employment Business established.

Table 3

Whether the Members in the Household Migrating in Search of Livelihood? (Before NREGS)

Sr. No	Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Yes	206	93.63
2	No	14	6.36
Total		220	100.00

Note. Source: Primary data

The responses pertaining to whether the members of the household are migrating in search of livelihood is presented in Table 3 before MGNREGS. It can be observed that a majority (n = 206, 94%) of the households believe that the members of the household

migrate in search of livelihoods. Only 6 per cent of the households indicated that the members of the household are not migrating in search of livelihoods.

The study found as per Table 4 shows that MGNREGS can help to control household migration. The majority of families (90%) believe that the MGNREGS will help to reduce household migration. There are just 10 percent of households that are on the other side.

Table 4

Whether MGNREGS could Help in Controlling the Migration of the Household?

Sr. No	Response	No. of Respondents	Percentage
1	Yes	198	90.00
2	No	22	10.00
	Total	220	100.00

Note. Source: Primary data

Table 5

Total Job Cards Issued Since Inception

Mandal Name	Panchayat Name	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20
Veldurthi	Patlaveedu	632	700	682	673
	Vajralapadu	415	447	468	445
	Veldurthy	1249	1263	1264	1247
	Total	2296	2410	2414	2365
Durgi	Adigoppula	1586	1568	1705	1680
	Rajanagar	403	403	419	422
	Terala	457	465	489	473
	Total	2446	2436	2613	2575
Grand total (6 Villages)		4742	4846	5027	4940

Note. Source: MGNREGS AP

Table 5 describes the overall performance of the growth of job cards issued, the movement in the issuance of job cards is decreasing but

then there is an ups and downs from 2016-17 to 2019-20.

Table 6

No of HH Provided Work in the following Financial Years

Mandal name	Panchayat Name	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20
Veldurthi	Patlaveedu	615	634	591	500
	Vajralapadu	541	566	580	574
	Veldurthy	988	1089	1116	983
	Total	2144	2289	2287	2057
Durgi	Adigoppula	741	857	751	711
	Rajanagar	403	314	296	346
	Terala	294	436	350	465
	Total	1438	1607	1397	1522
Grand Total (6 Villages)		3582	3896	3684	3579

Note. Source: MGNREGS AP

Table 7

Person Days Details of the Following Financial Years

Mandal name	Panchayat Name	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20
Veldurthi	Patlaveedu	37900	31588	26139	17146
	Vajralapadu	37449	38578	37234	26035
	Veldurthy	30359	41744	30464	22962
	Total	105708	111910	93837	66143
Durgi	Adigoppula	17749	25539	14879	16279
	Rajanagar	10504	11194	13675	14879
	Terala	12232	16650	23514	18571
	Total	40485	53383	52068	49729

Note. Source: MGNREGS AP

According to Table 6, for the last 4 years, there has been no significant change in the number of people getting work every year if we look at the details of those who got work in villages. It means that it can be observed that the Veldurthi Mandal same number of people are working every year. In the year 2016-17 in Veldurthi Mandal out of 2296 job cards 2144 people got work, similarly in 2017-18 out of 2410 job cards 2289 people got work. Also, in the rest of 2018-19, 2287 people got work for 2414 job cards, in 2019-20 2057 people got work for 2365 job cards. Similarly, the report informs that the situation in Durgi Mandal is that there are still less people who have got work.

A total of 19555 Job cards issued in two mandals (4742 in 2016-17, 4846 in 2017-18, 5027 in 2018-19 and 4940 in 2019-20) for 4 years in 6 villages of the study area. (3582 in 2016-17, 3896 in 2017-18, 3684 in 2018-19 and 3579 in 2019-20) to provided work to 14741 families as mentioned above 6 villages of 2 mandals during the 4 years.

As per Table 7, in Veldurthi Mandal it shows that 105708 person-days were done village wise in 2016-17 and increased in 2017-18 and gradually decreased for the remaining 2 years. Every year there should be growth but there is a record of decline. Based on this, it should be considered that there is an error in implementation. and there is no change in Durgi mandal also.

Table 8

Average Wage Per Day for the Following Financial Years

Mandal name	Panchayat Name	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20
	Wage per day (As per GoI) →				
Veldurthi	Patlaveedu	161.35	169.25	206.15	208.31
	Vajralapadu	163.56	169.73	202.59	205.13
	Veldurthy	153.44	141.67	196.12	191.47
Durgi	Adigoppula	122.14	104.81	184.79	189.91
	Rajanagar	175.62	164.27	202.66	194.07
	Terala	176.37	150.87	198.12	201.38

Note. Source: MGNREGS AP

In accordance in the Table 8 for the last 4 years, the average wage per day during 2016-17 it was Rs.194.00 wage per day but the wage seekers got only Rs.122.14 to 176.37 only. in the same way the wage remains to be like this in the remaining days. according to decision of the GOI in regard to wage for the wage seekers, it was like this which is as follows. 2016-17 -194.00, 2017-18 -197, 2018-19 -205.00, 2019-20 -211.00.

If we look at the wages fixed by the Government of India and the actual wages received by the labourers in the 4 years shown above,

the labourers did not get their full wages in any of the 6 villages in the above two mandals in any single year. Similarly, the Andhra Pradesh government spends extra on Cro bar and shovels in the implementation of the employment scheme and also deposits drinking water in their account. Rs.10 more wage should come. But it didn't happen that way. This should be seen as an implementation error. In this way wage earners are losing a large amount of wages in both villages and mandals at the district level and at the state level.

Table 9

No of HH Completed 100 Days in the Following Financial Years

Mandal name	Panchayat Name	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20
Veldurthi	Patlaveedu	135	92	133	110
	Vajralapadu	231	237	244	124
	Veldurthy	73	75	135	79
	Total	439	404	512	313
Durgi	Adigoppula	19	30	6	35
	Rajanagar	57	53	51	41
	Terala	116	106	160	106
	Total	192	189	217	182
Grand Total (6 Villages)		631	593	729	495

Note. Source: MGNREGS AP

Table 9 shows that (631 in 2016-17, 593 in 2017-18, 729 in 2018-19 and 495 in 2019-20) the House hold completed 100 days of employment in a year. The households employed under MGNREG scheme from 2016-17 to 2019-20 the number of households

completing 100 days each year has fluctuated. The above two mandals remain the same. While man days should increase every year, above four years should be observed with ups and downs. And the fourth year 2019-20 saw a sharp decline. Due to this, there is a

flaw in the implementation of the scheme. They are annual per capita. Expenditure on food, non-food, health, and education of children. It can have an impact on per capita savings.

According to primary data, the Employment Guarantee Scheme is useful for all wage seekers as well. But all these wage earners are families who have completed minimum 2 years out of four years 100 days' work completed. All of them are also happy to benefit from the employment guarantee scheme.

According to the secondary data there is a flaw in the implementation of the Employment Guarantee Scheme. The study was conducted on the beneficiaries of the beneficiary villages. If the rest of the villages are selected, there are more people who have not benefited from the employment guarantee scheme. So, if the implementing agencies focus fully on the rest of the villages and provide work to all, the employment guarantee scheme will be recognized, otherwise it will remain like other schemes.

Limitations of the Study

- This study is confined to Guntur district of Andhra Pradesh. It primarily focuses on MGNREGS beneficiaries residing in Veldurthi and Durgi mandals, who have completed at least 100 days of work in two or more years during the last four years 2016-17 to 2019-20.
- The analysis is based on information provided by the respondents regarding the impact of MGNREGS on enhancing the security and stability of their primary sources of household income.
- The findings of this study cannot be generalized to all districts of Andhra Pradesh, as the perceptions and experiences of respondents may vary across individuals and regions, depending on the nature and extent of MGNREGS implementation in those areas.
- The study focuses on beneficiaries who worked under MGNREGS during the period 2016-17 to 2019-20.

Further Research

The present study is confined to Guntur Rural area of Guntur District, Andhra Pradesh. The survey covered households that had completed at least 100 days of work in a minimum of two years out of the four-year period (2016-17 to 2019-20) under MGNREGS. Further research can be extended to a larger geographical area or to different regions to gain a broader understanding of the program's overall impact.

Future research may focus on the following areas:

- MGNREGS and its impact on rural migration in Andhra Pradesh
- MGNREGA and its influence on convergence works in Andhra Pradesh

- Women's empowerment through MGNREGS
- Experimental studies on how MGNREGS participation raises people's aspirations and improves their socioeconomic conditions, thereby contributing to better access to education and learning opportunities across various disciplines

Conclusion

NREGA has been in operation since 2006. Due to this scheme, the people of the rural areas are very economically useful. However, this paper discusses what will happen if the implementation is not done properly. This scheme is income support to poor families by Govt. Sponsored wage employment programs like NREGA in rural areas help reduce migration. It is a known fact that the more employment is available in rural areas, the less migration from rural areas to urban areas. But if everyone gets 100 days of work, wages as decided by the government, and if the work is done on the lands of the poor, then the scheme is well implemented. But this paper describes the implementation process in some villages. Therefore, the employment staff at the lower level should pay special attention to ensure that everyone is given 100 days of work and also ensure that the wages are received as determined by the government, then the objective of this scheme will be fulfilled.

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